

Larval Pyrethroids Resistance and Adult Knockdown Profile of *Anopheles gambiae* in Gusau, Zamfara State

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Abstract

Malaria is endemic in Nigeria with many states recording high cases all year round. Despite its public health significance, many states including Zamfara lacked adequate information on insecticide resistance status of malaria vector to guide evidence-based vector control program. To determine the larval pyrethroids resistance and adult knockdown profile of *Anopheles gambiae* population in Gusau, Zamfara state, Nigeria. Larval and adult bioassays using method of World Health Organisation (WHO) were carried out on sampled mosquitoes from two localities (Igala quarters and Tudun wada). Larval bioassay using Permethrin revealed moderate resistance ($LC_{50} = 0.127\text{mg/L}$ and $RR = 5.292$) in population of Igala quarters while high decrease in susceptibility to Permethrin in population of Tudun wada ($LC_{50} = 0.101\text{mg/L}$ and $RR = 4.208$) was observed. The adult susceptibility assay recorded poor knockdown in both Igala quarters and Tudun wada populations with highest percentage knockdown of 22.5% and 25% respectively. Highest KDT_{50} of 121.613 recorded was associated with Permethrin treatment of Igala quarters. The findings of the study indicated larval pyrethroid resistance with moderate resistance ratio (RR) and adult knockdown profile with high KDT_{50} value.

Keywords: Genomic DNA, Insecticides resistance, Knockdown, Pyrethroids

1.0 Introduction

Worldwide, malaria caused by *Plasmodium* parasite species, continues to be a serious public health issue. Female mosquitoes are the ones that transmit it [1]. It is projected that 241 million individuals distributed over 85 malaria-endemic countries were affected by malaria in 2020. This is an increase from 227 million in 2019, with the majority of this increase being from WHO member nations, mostly African region. Also, 27% of all the cases worldwide were in Nigeria [2]. In sub-Saharan Africa, the primary vector of *Plasmodium falciparum* (one of the most dangerous *Plasmodium* species) is the *Anopheles gambiae* complex [3]. Based on great abundance, lifespan, high inclination to feed humans, and great vectorial potential, *A. gambiae* is the

predominant and most effective vector of human malaria in the sub Saharan region [4].

The eight reproductively isolated species that make up the *A. gambiae* complex are: *A. amharicus*, *A. arabiensis*, *A. bwambae*, *A. coluzzii*, *A. gambiae sensu stricto* (s. s.), *A. melas*, *A. merus* and *A. quadriannulatus*, are morphologically indifferent [5]. Although they are morphologically similar and frequently sympatric, they differ genetically [6] and have different geographic ranges, larval ecology, behaviors, and dry season survival strategies [7].

In sub-Saharan Africa, *A. coluzzii*, *A. gambiae* s. s., *A. funestus*, and *A. arabiensis* are the most common malaria vectors [8]. According to Hinze [9], *A. gambiae* s. s., *A. arabiensis* and *A. coluzzii* are thought to have the greatest vectorial

capacity. According to ecological theory, *A. bwambae*, *A. melasand* and *A. merus*, are classified as saltwater or mineral water species since they can withstand salt, but the remaining species are obligate freshwater species [10].

In sub-Saharan Africa, *A. gambiae*, the primary malaria vector, has two molecular forms: Mopti (M) and Savanna (S) [11]. Nonetheless, Hinze[9] research revealed that these two molecular variants can be different species within the *A. gambiae* complex. According to recent reports, variations in a 4-Mb region (genomic island of divergence) in the X chromosome can identify the two molecular forms, designated M (*A. coluzzii*) and S (*A. gambiae* s. s.) and the majority of malaria transmission in Africa is caused by these two species [12].

However, for malaria vector control, the use of insecticide-based interventions has resulted in significant reductions in malaria morbidity and mortality [13], despite the threat of reverse gains due to other adaptive changes in mosquito populations and rising levels of insecticide resistance [14]. Numerous groups of insecticides have been created to manage mosquitoes and the illnesses they spread. These include the less common Neonicotinoids (Thiamethoxam, Thiachloprid, etc.), Organochlorine (DDT, endosulfan, etc.), Carbamates (Isoprocarb, Bendiocarb, Propoxur, etc.), Pyrethroids (Deltamethrin, Cypermethrin, Transfluthrin, Permethrin, etc.), Organophosphate (Chlorpyrifos, Primiphosmethyl, Malathion, Dimethoate, Dichlorvos, etc.), and Organophosphate (Ambiphosmethyl, Dimethoate, etc.). In several European nations, the first-generation insecticide dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) has contributed to the eradication or reduction of malaria [15]. More so, their efficacy has been limited due to the emergence of multiple cases of resistance brought about by their intensive and frequent use [16]. Moreover, numerous nations have banned it due to its high bioaccumulation capacity, environmental durability, and toxicity towards mammals [17, 18]. At the moment, pyrethroids are the most often used insecticides to control crop pests and other insects important to public health, such as mosquitoes [2]. Nonetheless, reports from West and East Africa indicated that *Anopheline* mosquitoes are resistant to pyrethroid insecticides [19]. Resistance to pyrethroid insecticides has been

documented in over 38 countries between 2010 and 2020, exhibiting varying intensities. As a result, this has emerged as a significant public health concern [2, 20].

Pyrethroids disrupt normal functioning of nerves of insect by changing kinetic of the voltage-sensitive sodium channels which mediate transitory increase in the sodium penetrability of nerve membrane during the rising phase of nerve action potential [21]. The pyrethroids target the central nervous system, their principal mechanism of action involves interacting with voltage-gated sodium channels (VGSCs) in neurons. The interaction results in depolarization due to the extended input of sodium ions. Extended depolarization is the cause of recurrent neuronal activity, which can be fatal and cause hyperexcitation [22]. It has also been discovered that certain pyrethroids suppress ATPase activity. Additionally, research has revealed that certain pyrethroids interact with the aminobutyric acid receptor; typically, type II pyrethroids exhibit this more frequently [23].

Mosquitoes-borne diseases are preventable, through protective measures which heavily relied on the use of chemical insecticides, notably pyrethroids, DDT and Organophosphates. According to Moyo [24] the use of insecticides account for 32.5% of all malaria preventive measures adopted in Zamfara State. Similarly, there is evidence demonstrating that the development of resistance in organisms is a dynamic phenomenon in time and space [25]. A better understanding of the molecular, ecological and evolutionary processes driving insecticides resistance in these vectors is essential to maximize the active lifespan of existing insecticides and to accelerate the development of new strategies and tools for vector control [26]. According to WHO, to guide insecticides resistance management, countries should develop and implement national insecticide resistance monitoring and management plan [2]. Therefore, the continuous monitoring and understanding the dynamics and spread of malaria vector insecticides resistance profiles and susceptibility status to help control the increasing malaria cases and other Mosquitoes borne diseases, necessitates this research.

The aim of this research is to investigate the larval pyrethroids resistance and adult

knockdown profile of *Anophelesgambiae* in Gusau, Zamfara State.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Gusau is geographically located on latitude (12.1628° N) and longitude (6.6745° E) and serves as the capital of Zamfara state in northwestern Nigeria. The state shares boundaries with Sokoto, Kebbi, Niger, Kaduna, Katsina states and Niger republic. Gusau town has an area of 3,364 km² and an estimated population of 383,162 as at 2006 census. Gusau has a tropical continental climate type, characterized by distinct wet (April – October) and dry (November – March) seasons with an average annual temperature of 30.22°C (86.4°F) [40].

2.2 Collection of Larvae/Pupae and Rearing of Mosquitoes

Larvae and pupae were collected directly from breeding site at two sampling sites (Igala quarters and Tudun Wada) by scooping-up with an entomological ladle and pipetting with Pasteur as described by Manrique-Saide [26]. The obtained samples were sorted and kept apart from other detritus and predators using plastic trays with shallow bottoms at a density of roughly 100/L of deionized water. Pupae were pipetted into tiny paper cups and placed in mosquito rearing cages, while larvae were given a diet consisting of ground dog biscuits, liver of beef, powdered-milk, and brewer's yeast in 2:1:1:1 ratio. Ten percent sucrose was sucked into cotton wool, and placed on the cage netting to feed the adult mosquitoes that had emerged. Conventional insect conditions were upheld, with temperature 27±2°C, a relative humidity (RH) of 75±10%, and a light dark cycle of 12:12 hours [1, 28].

2.3 Morphological Identification

Anopheles mosquitoes were identified morphologically using Stereo Zoom microscope 7X-45X Trinocular XTL as adopted by [29, 30]. Pictorial keys were also used in this process. The dark spot in the upper margins of wings, the palps being as long as the proboscis, the wings' blocks of black and white scales, the legs' speckles, the third preapical dark area on vein 1 with a pale of interruption, and the Tersi 1 to 4 with noticeable pale of bands were the main

features used for adult identification [29]. Smaller and slender with distinctive patterns of spots on the body, bristles and setae on the head and body, elongated and tapered abdomen with comb of bristles at the last segment, and very long and slender siphon were features common to larvae of *Anopheles* mosquitoes [29].

2.4 DNA Extraction

Genomic DNA was extracted using a procedure that has been developed by [31, 32]. 1.6 ml of 5M NaCl, 5.48 g sucrose, 1.57 g Tris, 10.16 EDTA ml 0.5M, 2.5 ml SDS20%, and distilled sterile and deionized water were used to generate the Livak grinding buffer. The volume of solution was then increased to 100 ml. After sterilizing and filtering, the solution was sub-aliquoted and kept at -20°C. A single mosquito was homogenized in 1.5 mL of preheated Livak grinding buffer using operated battery mortar and pestle (SIGMA), and the homogenate was then immediately incubated at 65°C for 30 minutes. Following the incubation period, the condensation was collected using a quick microcentrifuge, and 14 µL of potassium acetate (8 M) was added to reach a 1M final concentration of. After pulsating vortexing the samples, they were incubated on ice for almost half an hour. After centrifuging the tubes for 20 minutes at 4 °C at 15,000 rpm, the supernatant was carefully transferred to a fresh 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube. After adding 200µL of ethanol 100%, the mixture was centrifuged once more for 15 minutes at 4 °C and 15,000 rpm. The pellets were then rinsed with 100µL of 70% ice-cold ethanol, allowed to air dry approximately an hour and then again suspended in 100µL distilled water. The supernatant was disposed of at this point. Finally, the pellets (DNA) were incubated for 10 minutes at 65 °C [33].

2.5 Molecular Identification of Mosquitoes

Intergenic sequence (IGS) sections of ribosomal DNA (rDNA) were amplified using the primers IGS441 Forward (5'-TGG TCT GGG GAC CAC GTC GAC ACA GG-3') and IGS783 Reverse (5'-CGT TTC TCA CAT CAA GACAAT CAA GTC-3') [34, 35]. KAPA Taq DNA polymerase was used in the PCR reaction. 1µL of genomic DNA, 1.5µL of 10 Taq A Buffer, about 0.4M (0.51µL) of forward and reverse primer, 1.25mM of MgCl₂, 0.25mM of dNTP mixes, and 0.12µL

of Taq DNA polymerase in ddH₂O made up the reaction mix. The conditions for amplification were as follows: Denaturation at 95 °C for 5 minutes followed by 35 cycles of final denaturation at 95 °C for 30 seconds, annealing at 51 °C for 40 seconds, extension at 72 °C for 60 seconds and final extension at 72 °C for 10 minutes. One unit of MseI and one unit of 1× of buffer 2 (New England Biolabs Beverly, MA) are added to the PCR following amplification. The PCR amplicons were separated in 1.5 % agarose gel electrophoresis pre-stained with ethidium bromide for 35 minutes at 110 volts.

2.6 Pyrethroids Susceptibility Test of Larvae (Larval bioassay)

Larval bioassay were carried out according to the protocol provided by WHO [1] with little modification. One millilitre (1ml) of 1.0 mg/ml of technical grade deltamethrin and Permethrin (Sigma Aldrich-Pestanall, Seelze, Germany) were diluted in 10ml of absolute ethanol from which 1 ml was mixed with 99 ml of distilled water, the first working solution was serially diluted by 50 % to obtain the subsequent concentrations. Four replicates of 20 larvae (3rd and 4th) were introduced to separate test cups for 24 hours. Mortalities were recorded 24 hours post-exposure to the insecticides by recording both the dead and the moribund (those incapable of swimming up to the surface or unable to dive when the water is disturbed) larvae as dead. Using probit analysis and SPSS version 20 software, the lethal concentrations that kill 50% (LC₅₀) of the studied populations were determined.

2.7 Pyrethroids Susceptibility Test of Adult Mosquitoes (Knockdown Profile)

The adult bioassays were carried out using WHO bioassay tube according to protocol provided by WHO [1]. Under usual insectary conditions, four replicates of twenty adult *A. gambiae* were subjected for sixty minutes to filter paper saturated with 0.75% Permethrin and 0.05% Deltamethrin. Number of mosquitoes that were knocked down after 15, 30, 45, and 60 minutes of exposure was recorded.

2.7 Data Analysis

Using SPSS version 20, a linear probit analysis of the larval bioassay results for LC₅₀ was carried

out. The resistance ratio (RR) was determined by dividing the computed LC₅₀ by the LC₅₀ from the totally susceptible laboratory population, New Orleans. Using Microsoft Excel 2010, the WHO tube bioassay findings and graphs were analyzed. Using SPSS version 20, a linear probit analysis of the adult bioassay results for KDT₅₀ was also carried out.

3.0 Results

3.1 Morphological and Molecular Identification

Larvae and adult mosquitoes were identified based on morphological characteristics utilizing pictorial keys as *Anopheles gambiae*. Polymerase chain reaction-based molecular identification method confirmed the mosquito's population composed of *A. gambiae* s. (the S molecular form of *A. gambiae*) and *A. coluzzii* (the M molecular form of *A. gambiae*). The PCR product of mosquitoes when electrophoresed had band size of 288 bp and 181 bp (Plate 3.1).

Plate 3.1: Gel Electrophoresis of PCR products of *A. gambiae* Identification. Lane 1: 1kb ladder, lane 2: negative control, lane 3 & 4: band indicating *A. gambiae* s. s. (288 bp) and *A. coluzzii* (181 bp)

3.2 Insecticide Susceptibility Test of *A. gambiae* Larvae

Result of larval bioassays conducted with Deltamethrin showed no resistance in mosquito populations of Igala quarters and Tudun wada with LC₅₀ (0.038mg/L), RR (1.58) and LC₅₀ (0.036), RR (1.50) respectively (Table 3.1). Slight decrease in susceptibility to Deltamethrin

was observed when compared to known laboratory susceptible colony (New Orleans) ($LC_{50} = 0.024$). However, there was high decrease in susceptibility to Permethrin in mosquito population at Tudun wada with LC_{50} (0.101mg/L) and RR (4.208) and moderate resistance to Permethrin in mosquito population of Igala quarters ($LC_{50} = 0.127$ mg/L and RR = 5.292) (Table 3.1).

The percentage mortality of larvae from Tudun wada was slightly higher than that recorded in Igala quarters for both Permethrin ($p = 0.390$, $t = -0.926$, $df = 6$) and Deltamethrin ($p = 0.238$, $t = -1.309$, $df = 6$). Similarly, higher mortality was recorded when larvae were exposed to Deltamethrin than Permethrin at 0.05mg/L (Figure 3.1).

3.3 Insecticide Susceptibility Test of Adult *A. gambiae* (Knockdown Profile)

The result of adult bioassay showed low percentage knockdown (poor knockdown) at both Igala quarters and Tudun wada. The highest percentage knockdown of 22.5% and 25% were recorded with Deltamethrin treatment at Igala quarters and Tudun wada respectively (Figure 3.2 and 3.3). The rates of knockdown recorded with Permethrin and Deltamethrin increased with time in both locations. However, more knockdowns were recorded with Deltamethrin than Permethrin in both locations. Similarly, higher knockdown was observed at Tudun wada compared to Igala quarters when adult mosquitoes were exposed to both insecticides. The least KDT_{50} (96.213) recorded was associated with Deltamethrin treatment at Tudun wada while the highest KDT_{50} (121.613) recorded was associated with Permethrin treatment at Igala quarters (Table 3.2).

Table 3.1: Susceptibility of *A. gambiae* Larvae to Permethrin and Deltamethrin

Location	Insecticide	N	SE	LC_{50} (mg/L) (95% CI)	X^2	P	RR
Igala quarters	Permethrin	100	0.404	0.127(0.64-2.072)	1.204	0.752	5.292
	Deltamethrin	100	0.397	0.038 (0.027-0.059)	0.566	0.904	1.58
Tudun wada	Permethrin	100	0.449	0.101(0.56-0.810)	0.033	0.004	4.208
	Deltamethrin	100	0.448	0.036(0.028-0.048)	2.037	0.565	1.50

SE = standard error of mean; LC_{50} = lethal concentration that killed 50% of the larvae; CI = confidence interval; X^2 = Chi Square test; p = level of significance value; and RR = resistance ratio; N = number of larvae exposed.

Figure 3.1: Percentage mortality of larval bioassays

Figure 3.2: Knockdown Profile of *A. gambiae* from Igala quarters

Figure 3.3: Knockdown Profile of *A. gambiae* from Tudun wada

Table 3.2: Knockdown time of the *A. gambiae* exposed to pyrethroid.

Insecticides	Igala quarters				Tudun wada			
	N	KDT ₅₀	X ²	P	N	KDT ₅₀	X ²	P
Permethrin	80	121.613	0.435	0.85	80	103.127	0.524	0.770
Deltamethrin	80	103.776	0.713	0.700	80	96.213	0.928	0.629

KDT₅₀ = time (min) taken to knockdown 50% of the mosquitoes; N = number of mosquitoes exposed; X² = Chi Square test; p = level of significance value.

4.0 Discussion

The resistant profile of the leading vector species must be identified in order to effectively direct the use of insecticides in the malaria vector control programs. This makes it possible to select an insecticide judiciously depending on the kind and degree of resistance that is already present. Gusau which is the capital of Zamfara state located in north western Nigeria characterized with high fluctuation of weather that favour seasonal transmission of malaria as well as seasonal abundance of malaria vector, offers greater chance of malaria elimination and vector control.

Unfortunately, malaria is still endemic in the region and Nigeria at large.

A. gambiae s. s. and *A. coluzzii* were the members of the *A. gambiae* complex identified molecularly in the study area and during the rainy season (period of peak malaria transmission). Ibrahim [26] identified *A. coluzzii* as the primary malaria vector in northern Nigeria, while Akpan [36] discovered *A. gambiae* s. s. among the *A. gambiae* complex that is spread throughout Zamfara state. In Taraba state, northeastern Nigeria, Lamidi [37] similarly discovered that the prevalent species within the *A. gambiae* complex were *A. coluzzii* and *A. gambiae* s. s. These species are particularly

abundant in these areas due to the diurnal temperature range, which makes the species more sensitive to climatic changes and leads to a vast distribution of the species [36].

The larval susceptibility test (larval bioassay) demonstrated moderate resistance to Permethrin and very low of resistance (but with high decrease in susceptibility) to Deltamethrin. Findings from previous research by Mukhtar and Ibrahim [33] showed that resistance to pyrethroid by mosquito larvae are dramatically increasing with LC_{50} (0.018 – 0.198mg/L). There was more mortality in larval bioassays conducted with Deltamethrin than Permethrin in both study sites, this may be attributed to the fact that Permethrin is the most widely used pyrethroid as commercial insecticides for residual spraying and long-lasting insecticidal nets [26].

The higher KDT_{50} found for both Deltamethrin and Permethrin was strongly corroborated by the low percentage knockdown (poor knockdown) seen during adult bioassay. According to Medjigbodo [38], high KDT_{50} values in field mosquitoes indicate early resistance to the insecticides used. Furthermore, the decrease in mortality that was observed is correlated with the high value of KDT_{50} observed, indicating that KDT_{50} can be a useful marker for the early identification of pyrethroid resistance. Also, Ononamadu [39] found similar observation of a high KDT_{50} value in Kano.

5.0 Conclusion

The study confirmed the abundance of the major malaria vector *A. gambiae* s. s. and *A. coluzzii* in Gusau, Zamfara state. The larvae of *A. gambiae* resistance to Deltamethrin and Permethrin with moderate resistance ratio were ascertained by larval bioassays conducted. The high KDT_{50} value recorded also reaffirmed the presence of resistance to the pyrethroids used (Permethrin and Deltamethrin) which also presented early indication of resistance in adult mosquitoes. These records of pyrethroid resistance in *A. gambiae* pose a serious threat to the reduction of malaria cases. It is of great importance to continue reporting this resistance and its underlying mechanisms from these locations to guide effective evidence-based malaria control solutions.

6.0 Recommendations

In order to eradicate malaria and other mosquito vector borne diseases, it is paramount to control the bionomics and genomics of the mosquito vector, so that the cycle of the diseases is broken. More so, there is need for continuous profiling of resistance status of the mosquito vector for baseline information that will guide the selection of insecticides to be used.

7.0 Reference

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